

Acknowledgement

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of 4-oxa isomer, the C₂-protons would have appeared at much higher field⁶. C₄-protons being devoid of any vicinal hydrogen appeared as two doublets^{7,8} (see Experimental).

Similar treatment of 2 provided methyl 6-oxa-5-oxo-3,5-seco-4-nor-B-homocholestan-3-oate (6) and 3-oxa-4-oxo-4a,5-oxido-5ξ-cholestan-6β-yl chloride (7). The compound 6 gave negative Beilstein test and its spectral data (ir and pmr, see Experimental) were compatible with the structure 6. Formation of the compound 6 indicates that it follows the same mechanistic route (Scheme 1) as reported¹ in the case of its 6β-bromo analogue.

Perbenzoic Acid Oxidation of some 3-Oxosteroids

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IN continuation to our work on the synthetic steroids¹⁻³, the Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of some 3-ketosteroids, such as 3-oxo-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestan-6β-yl chloride (1), 3-oxocholest-4-en-6β-yl chloride (2)⁴ and 3-oxocholesta-1,4-diene (3)⁵ has been presently undertaken to evaluate the effect of neighbouring substituent on the product outcome.

The ketone (1) on treatment with perbenzoic acid in the presence of catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid gave 3-oxa-4-oxo-*A*-homocholest-5-ene (4) and 3-oxa-4-oxo-*A*-homo-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestan-6β-yl chloride (5). The structures 4 and 5 were preferred over their 4-oxa analogues on the basis of pmr spectra. The signal at δ 4.23 and 4.2 for C2-H₂ in 4 and 5, respectively, indicated the presence of 3-oxa moiety⁶. In the case

Scheme 1

Compound 7 was analysed for C₂₇H₄₃O₃Cl. Its ir spectra showed the presence of oxido group

and ϵ -lactone (see Experimental). In pmr spectra, C_{α} -proton signal appearing at δ 4.25, supported the presence of 3-oxa moiety⁶ in the compound.

Compound 3 under similar conditions failed to provide either of the expected ϵ -lactone 9 or 10, instead, only the epoxide (8) was obtained. 4,5-Epoxide is preferred over the possible 1,2-epoxide on the basis of its pmr spectra, showing the presence of two vinylic protons, which is compatible with the structure 8.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian A60 instrument with TMS as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel and sprayed with aqueous 20% perchloric acid solution. Light petroleum refers to fraction, b.p. 60–80°.

Reaction of 1 with perbenzoic acid: To a solution of the ketone (1; 1.5 g) in chloroform (20 ml), containing catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, was added a solution of perbenzoic acid (2 mol equiv.) in chloroform. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 14 days, till the reaction was complete (monitored by tlc). The solvent was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with water, aqueous sodium bicarbonate (5%), water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent gave an oil (ca 1.5 g) which was chromatographed over silica gel (30 g) (fractions of ~25 ml collected). Elution with light petroleum-ether (20 : 1) furnished 4 which was crystallised from methanol (300 mg), m.p. 184° (Found : C, 80.8 ; H, 11.0. $C_{27}H_{44}O_3$ requires : C, 80.94 ; H, 11.07%), negative Beilstein test ; ν_{max} 1 735 (ϵ -lactone) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=C) ; δ 5.63 (1H, m, C_{α} -H), 4.23 (2H, m, C_{β} -H₂), 3.16 and 2.46 (each 1H, d, *J* 18 Hz, $C_{\alpha\beta}$ -H₂, AB system centred at 2.8), 1.23, 0.9, 0.81 and 0.72 (CH_3).

Further elution with light petroleum-ether (1 : 1) gave 5 which was crystallised from methanol (400 mg), m.p. 238° (Found : C, 74.2 ; H, 10.3 ; $C_{27}H_{44}O_3Cl$ requires : C, 74.19 ; H, 10.37%) ; positive Beilstein test ; ν_{max} 3 500–3 420 (OH), 1 720 (ϵ -lactone) and 720 cm^{-1} (C-Cl) ; δ 4.2 (2H, C_{β} -H₂), 3.6 and 2.7 d (each 1H, d, *J* 15 Hz, $C_{\alpha\beta}$ -H₂, AB system centred at 3.1), 3.2 (1H, m, *J* 3 Hz, C_{α} -H), 1.3, 1.2, 0.9, 0.8 and 0.7 (CH_3).

Reaction of 2 with perbenzoic acid: To a solution of the ketone (2) in chloroform (20 ml), containing *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as a catalyst, was added a solution of perbenzoic acid (2 mol equiv.) in chloroform. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 10 days and worked up as described for the ketone 1. An oil (ca 1.5 g) was obtained which was chromatographed over silica gel (30 g) (fractions of ~25 ml collected). Elution with light petroleum-ether

(10 : 1) furnished 6 which was crystallised from light petroleum (350 mg), m.p. 140° (Found : C, 74.7 ; H, 10.6. $C_{27}H_{44}O_4$ requires : C, 74.60 ; H, 10.66%), negative Beilstein test ; ν_{max} 1 730 (ϵ -lactone) and 1 750 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl) ; δ 4.17 (2H, m, C_{β} -H₂), 3.66 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.17 (2H, m, C_{α} -H₂), 1.3, 0.93, 0.83 and 0.7 (other CH_3).

Further elution with light petroleum-ether (5 : 1) provided 7 as a non-crystallisable oil (400 mg) (Found : C, 71.8 ; H, 9.5. $C_{27}H_{43}O_3Cl$ requires : C, 71.89 ; H, 9.6%) ; positive Beilstein test ; ν_{max} 1 730 (ϵ -lactone), 870 cm^{-1} (epoxide)^{7,8}, 750 cm^{-1} (C-Cl) ; δ 4.25 (2H, C_{β} -H₂), 3.72 (1H, m, *J* 4 Hz, C_{α} -H), 3.66 (1H, s, $C_{\alpha\beta}$ -H), 1.2, 0.93, 0.83 and 0.71 (CH_3).

Reaction of 3 with perbenzoic acid: To a solution of 3 (1.0 g) in chloroform (15 ml), containing *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as the catalyst, was added a solution of perbenzoic acid (2 mol equiv.) in chloroform. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 15 days. Usual work up afforded 8 which was crystallised from methanol (800 mg), m.p. 125° (Found : C, 81.4 ; H, 10.4. $C_{27}H_{42}O_3$ requires : C, 81.35 ; H, 10.62%) ; ν_{max} 1 690 (α, β -unsaturated ketone), 1 620 (C=C) and 870 cm^{-1} (epoxide)^{7,8} ; δ 6.4 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, C_{α} -H), 5.7 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, C_{β} -H), 3.65 (s, C_{α} - β H), 1.2, 0.9, 0.8 and 0.7 (CH_3).

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